

Best Planning Practices for Ultra-High-Capacity Networks based on Multi-Band over Space Division Multiplexing

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Abstract We evaluate best planning practices for MBoSDM optical networks using four-core MCFs over C-, C+L-, C+S-, and C+L+S-bands. Results show that C+L offers optimal spectral efficiency, while C+L+S achieves maximum capacity with lowest blocking, balancing performance and deployment complexity. ©2025 The Author(s)

Introduction

Expanding transmission beyond the conventional C-band into adjacent spectral regions such as the L- and S-bands can increase the usable optical bandwidth to approximately 20 THz^[1]. At the same time, spatial multiplexing using multi-core fibers (MCFs) provides a compact and scalable means of multiplying transmission capacity within a single fiber, without proportionally increasing the physical infrastructure^[2]. The integration of these two approaches—referred to as multi-band (MB) over space division multiplexing (MBoSDM)—emerges as a key architectural strategy for future optical networks^[3].

Multiple research initiatives have explored such systems to support emerging ultra-bandwidth applications including 6G communications, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence^[4]. Notably, the SEASON project aims to design and validate energy-efficient, ultra-high-capacity transport networks^[5]. Within this context, establishing planning practices that reflect both the maturity of current technologies and realistic performance targets is essential. However, to enable the deployment of MBoSDM-based systems, compatible network elements—such as amplifiers, multiplexers, and transceivers—must be developed or adapted to support the extended spectral and spatial domains^[6]. Prior to this, telecom operators need clear insight into the potential opportunities and limitations of MBoSDM in terms of key performance indicators such as network throughput and blocking probability. These metrics are essential for evaluating migration strategies and identifying the most efficient planning scenarios for future network evolution. In planning ultra-high-capacity optical networks based on MBoSDM, it

is essential to consider the frequency-dependent nature of key physical-layer parameters^[1]. The loss coefficient, dispersion, effective area, nonlinearities, Raman gain, intercore crosstalk (ICXT), amplifier gain profiles, and noise figures all vary with wavelength^[3]. As a result, the quality of transmission (QoT) of a given lightpath is not solely determined by distance and modulation format, but also by the specific frequency of each channel. Consequently, the usable working zone of the system shifts with each band extension, requiring per-band optimization. This complexity makes careful scenario evaluation critical for operators aiming to balance spectral efficiency, capacity scaling, and service quality across evolving transmission bands. From an operator's perspective, best practices must also account for deployment maturity and migration strategy. While C-band-only systems are well-established, the C+L-band configuration has already reached commercial deployment and is currently the most viable option for near-term spectrum expansion.

This work focuses on a practical subset of MB configurations—specifically, C-band, C+L-band, C+S-band, and C+L+S-band transmissions—over weakly-coupled four-core MCFs with a standard 125 μm cladding diameter^[7]. We present a comprehensive performance evaluation of these configurations to derive best-practice planning strategies, with particular emphasis on balancing throughput improvement, system capacity, and blocking probability. By establishing a clear performance roadmap for MBoSDM-enabled optical networks, this study supports the strategic evolution of future-ready optical network infrastructures. Several recent studies have explored the potential of combining MB operation and SDM to address

the scalability needs of optical networks^{[7]–[15]}. Previous work compared MCF-based networks with conventional single-mode fiber (SMF) bundles, showing significant gains in spatial efficiency and potential cost savings when ICXT is effectively managed^[3]. Furthermore, recent research has emphasized the critical importance of ultra-low ICXT fibers, particularly in MB scenarios, where nonlinear effects such as inter-channel stimulated Raman scattering (ISRS) can exacerbate crosstalk penalties. Moreover, N. Sambo et al.^[16] evaluated the blocking probability of various MB configurations—such as C-band, C+L-band, and C+L+S-band—over SMFs. However, a similar study for MBoSDM systems has not yet been conducted. We analyze the network throughput of the above-mentioned subset of MBoSDM configurations over the U.S. backbone topology and show that the C+L+S-band scenario achieves up to 175% higher throughput compared to the C-band, 34% higher than C+L-band, and 42% higher than C+S-band.

Physical Layer Modeling

We model the physical layer impairments of MBoSDM networks based on trench-assisted weakly-coupled four-core MCFs with a standard cladding diameter of 125 μm . The model incorporates key linear and nonlinear noise sources, including amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) noise, nonlinear interference (NLI) from Kerr effects, ICXT, and ISRS penalties. The QoT for a lightpath is estimated using the generalized signal-to-noise ratio (GSNR), expressed as:

$$GSNR_{LP}|_{\text{dB}} = 10 \log_{10} \left[(SNR_{ASE}^{-1} + SNR_{NLI}^{-1} + SNR_{ICXT}^{-1} + SNR_{TRX}^{-1})^{-1} \right] - \sigma_{\text{Flt}}|_{\text{dB}} - \sigma_{\text{Ag}}|_{\text{dB}}, \quad (1)$$

where SNR_{ASE} , SNR_{NLI} , and SNR_{ICXT} represent the signal-to-noise ratios limited by ASE noise, NLI, and ICXT, respectively. SNR_{TRX} accounts for the transceiver noise contribution, while σ_{Flt} and σ_{Ag} are penalties associated with wavelength-selective switch filtering and system aging, respectively. Nonlinear impairments are estimated using a semi-closed-form enhanced generalized Gaussian noise model, which accurately captures the impact of Kerr and ISRS nonlinearities in wideband systems^{[17],[18]}. The ICXT power for each channel is estimated using a frequency-dependent model adapted for trench-assisted MCFs, as explained in detail in our previous work^[3].

Best Planning Practices for MBoSDM Systems: Methodology, Simulations, and Conclusions

This study evaluates the performance of four representative transmission scenarios based on spectrum expansion strategies: **C-band only** with 80 channels over 6 THz, **C+L-band** with 160 channels over 12 THz, **C+S-band** with 188 channels

over 14 THz, and **C+L+S-band** with 268 channels over 20 THz. The analysis is conducted using a physical-layer-aware simulation framework for **MBoSDM** optical networks. We consider a realistic long-haul topology based on the US backbone network with 60 nodes^[3]. Each link is modeled with band-specific fiber parameters, including frequency-dependent attenuation, dispersion, effective area, nonlinear coefficient, Raman gain spectrum, amplifier gain profiles, and noise figures (for more details regarding the physical layer parameters, see^[3].) Each link uses a fixed grid with 75 GHz channel spacing and 64 GBaud symbol rates, supporting modulation formats ranging from PM-BPSK to PM-64QAM with bit rate 100 to 600 Gbps per channel depending on the GSNR, respectively.

The network throughput, spectral efficiency, and blocking probability are computed across 91 core-to-core connections using the first three shortest paths. It should be noted that only the 14 main (core) datacenter nodes are equipped with add/drop functionality, while the remaining nodes do not support add/drop operations^[8]. These scenarios are selected to reflect both currently deployed systems (C and C+L) and near-future options (C+S and C+L+S), offering insight into the trade-offs between capacity scaling and operational complexity in practical MBoSDM networks. For the bandwidth blocking probability (BBP) analysis, request inter-arrival and holding times are modeled using exponential distributions. Bandwidth demands are uniformly distributed between 100 and 600 Gbps, in increments of 100 Gbps. Average BBP values are computed either upon reaching a 95% confidence interval or after completing a maximum of 50 independent simulation runs (seeds). To ensure statistical reliability, each iteration includes 150,000 connection requests for networks configured with four cores. Simulation results verify that the network reaches a steady state under these traffic volumes, thereby ensuring the consistency and robustness of the measured outcomes. The BBP is defined as the ratio of the total blocked bandwidth to the total requested bandwidth throughout the simulation. This metric captures the fraction of aggregate bandwidth demand that cannot be fulfilled due to resource constraints, such as unavailable spectral slots, cores, or modulation formats. Figure 1(a)–(d) illustrates the modulation format index for each connection/lightpath using the first shortest path. Each color corresponds to a modulation format level (MFL) determined by the GSNR thresholds, ranging from QPSK ($m = 1$) to 64QAM ($m = 6$). Channel indices are segmented by band and visually separated using vertical dividers and colored arrows. As expected, the MFL tends to degrade toward

Fig. 1: (Top) Modulation format level distributions per channel for each MBoSDM configuration across 91 connections. (Bottom) Cumulative bit rate distribution per connection index and the corresponding transmission distance.

Fig. 2: (a) Network total throughput for different MBoSDM scenarios, (b)BBP of different solutions in L+C+S multi-band network under different traffic loads

the higher frequency channels (S-band) due to increased attenuation and Raman-induced power tilt. Among all cases, the C+L+S-band exhibits the most diversified GSNR distribution, driven by inter-band power imbalance and ISRS effects. The bottom subplot of Fig. 1 presents the cumulative bit rate (dashed lines) and transmission distance (bars) per Lighthpath index. The C and C + L bands show more stable performance because of the favorable loss characteristics and the availability of low-noise amplifiers. In contrast, the S-band reveals wider GSNR variations and more conservative modulation formats due to higher attenuation and amplifier noise figures. Although

the C+S-band includes more channels (188 vs. 160 in C+L), its cumulative throughput for long-haul lightpaths (over 1000 km) is lower. This is mainly due to three factors: higher attenuation in the S-band, increased amplifier noise, and ISRS-induced power tilt which depletes higher-frequency channels. For short-distance connections (under 1000 km), however, the S-band performs well, as ISRS penalties are less pronounced. As distance increases, particularly beyond 3000 km, the cumulative throughput drops sharply due to amplified ISRS effects. Figure 2(a) presents the total network capacity for each scenario. The C+L+S configuration achieves 34% more total capacity than C+L, while using 67% more channels. Compared to C+S, the C+L+S scenario yields both a 42% increase in capacity and a 42% increase in channel count. Between C+L and C+S, the former outperforms the latter, offering a 104% capacity gain over the C-band baseline, versus 92% for C+S. These results indicate that despite higher ICXT in the L-band, it does not significantly affect overall throughput. Instead, the loss coefficient, ISRS, and amplifier noise have a greater impact on performance. The normalized capacity per Hz, shown on the right axis of Fig. 2(a), confirms this: C+L yields the highest bit rate efficiency, aligning with earlier observations. Figure 2(b) shows the average BBP under dynamic service provisioning for all scenarios. As expected, C+L+S results in the lowest blocking probability due to its large spectral space, while C+L performs better than C+S and significantly better than the C-band. These insights guide operators in selecting optimal configurations for scalable and efficient optical network evolution.

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